

Silicon is considered a critical raw material for the EU due to its high supply risk and economic importance, mainly because of heavy reliance on imports. The objective of RESiLEX is to improve the resilience and sustainability of the entire Silicon value chain and reduce EU dependence on critical raw materials for solar panel and battery production.

Solar cells with reduced critical raw materials

Silicon heterojunction (SHJ) solar cell technology represents a highly promising pathway for next-generation industrial photovoltaic production. SHJ technology is valued for its high efficiency, low-temperature manufacturing process (below 230 °C), and a reduced number of process steps. However, the rapid expansion of the photovoltaic sector (with projected SHJ production capacity exceeding 218 GW/year in the near future) is constrained by the limited availability and price volatility of certain strategic elements used in SHJ cells.

The main critical elements examined in the context of Resilex are:

- **Indium (In):** Used in Indium Tin Oxide (ITO), the industrial standard for the Transparent Conductive Oxide (TCO) layer. The limited supply of indium could cap annual SHJ production at just 95 GW, by allocating 20% of the global supply.
- **Silver (Ag):** Used for the metallic grid. The high consumption of Ag in SHJ cells (historically 24.6 mgAg/Wp at the start of the project) could cap SHJ production at around 171 GW/year (allocating 20% of the 2019 global supply).
- **Silicon (Si):** The reduction of silicon consumption (by using thinner wafers) is a key lever for decreasing the environmental impact of silicon-based cells, due to the intense energy consumption required for its purification and fabrication.

The goal of the RESiLEX project is to analyze the performance and raise the maturity (TRL) of solutions (from TRL 5 to TRL 7) that aim to develop In-less/In-free, Ag-less/Ag-free solar cells and the use of thin silicon wafers.

Pathways for Indium reduction

The strategies studied for reducing indium in the Transparent Conductive Oxide (TCO) of SHJ cells include:

- **Thickness Reduction (In-less):** The most mature approach has shown the possibility of reducing the Indium content in SHJ cells by 77.2% compared to the standard configuration, with an efficiency loss of less than 0.1% absolute. This result was achieved using ultrathin ITO layers (15 nm on the front and 30 nm on the back) in combination with a dielectric anti-reflection coating (DARC) layer.
- **Replacement with Indium-Free TCO (In-free):** Aluminum-doped Zinc Oxide (AZO) and Tin Dioxide (SnO_2) were explored. The integration of a "Front In-free" architecture (AZO on the front) was successfully demonstrated on the CEA pilot line, with no loss of efficiency. However, the readiness level of this approach remains lower than (In-less) cells due to stability issues of AZO layers. The deposition of thin SnO_2 films was developed using the AP-SALD (Atmospheric Pressure Spatial Atomic Layer Deposition) technique, a non-vacuum method with a low environmental footprint, although electron mobility remains a key limitation.

Silver is used for the metallic grid of solar panels

Pathways for Silver reduction

The two main strategies for Silver reduction are:

- **Screen-printing with Copper/Silver (Ag/Cu) Pastes:** Partially replacing silver with silver-coated copper particles. The results demonstrated the feasibility of achieving a total silver consumption of 10.9 mgAg/Wp (a 55% reduction compared to the initial industrial reference of 24.6 mgAg/Wp), while maintaining a limited efficiency loss of 0.04% absolute.
- **Copper Electroplating (Cu Plating):** A radically different approach that allows for the complete elimination of silver (Ag-free). The process uses a thin seed grid and a subsequent dielectric layer that acts as a plating mask and anti-reflection coating (ARC).

Tested solutions

Resilex partners tested the feasibility of scenarios that combine the reduction of Indium and Silver, aiming to reach 25% efficiency compatible with mass production.

- **Scenario 1** (In-less + Ag/Cu Paste): A combined reduction of 72% for Indium and 62% for Silver was demonstrated on consistent batches, with a median absolute efficiency loss of only 0.3%. This result is compatible with 25% efficiencies on industrial lines. The TRL of this approach has been raised to TRL 7.
- **Scenario 2** (In-less + Cu Plating): A combination of a 72% Indium reduction with Copper metallization via electroplating (Ag-free) was achieved. The absolute efficiency loss was extremely limited (only 0.23%), confirming the compatibility of this process with 25% mass efficiencies. Additionally, it was shown that the dielectric layer used for Cu plating can simultaneously serve for TCO re-hydrogenation and as a mask.

As for the reduction of Silicon, the compatibility of the SHJ process (even in the "In-less" version) with the use of thin wafers (down to 65 μm) was confirmed, while maintaining a high open-circuit voltage (Voc). The SHJ architecture, thanks to its excellent surface passivation and low-temperature processing, is intrinsically suitable for the use of ultra-thin wafers.

Conclusions

Results from the performed tests confirm the technical feasibility of the solutions developed in Resilex for a drastic reduction in Indium, Silver and Silicon consumption in SHJ cells, with a negligible performance loss. These developments raise the technological maturity (TRL 7) of the approach based on the reduced use of Indium, Silver and Silicon, paving the way for the sustainable mass production of high-efficiency photovoltaic cells in Europe.

